

Synthesis of some xanthato-complexes

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Potassium 2-trithiocarbonatoethyl xanthate and its complexes of the type $C_4H_4OS_5M.2H_2O$ ($M = Mn^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}$) and $C_4H_4OS_5Cl.FeH_2O$ have been prepared. All the complexes are found to be paramagnetic and high-spin having octahedral geometry. IR studies showed M-S bonding and coordinated water.

Synthesis and characterization of bimetallic xanthate¹ as well as physicochemical studies of some bimetallic mixed-ligand complexes containing a bis-bidentate ONNO Schiff base and alkyl xanthate have been reported². Nahar *et al.*³ proposed octahedral geometry to Sb^{III} -bis(di-isopropylthio-orthophosphate)alkyl xanthate (Et, Pr, ⁱPr, Bu, ⁱBu). Spectrochemical investigations and adsorption studies of ethyl xanthate on coinage metals have been reported^{4,5}. Effects of the hydrazine and Pd^{II} addition on the formation kinetics and stability of ⁹⁹Tc complex with ethyl xanthate were studied⁶ in aqueous HNO_3 . A survey of literature on xanthates have revealed that the studies so far conducted are neither comprehensive nor systematic and much work has to be required to understand the chemistry of metal-sulfur bonds in xanthato-complexes. Keeping in mind the reaction of both mercaptan⁷ and alcoholic group⁸ with carbon disulfide and alkali in stoichiometric quantities, it is thought worthwhile to synthesize polydentate chelating agent, derived from 2-mercaptoethanol according to the following reaction :

Results and discussion

Aqueous solution of the metal salts mixed with aqueous solution of PTEX produced colour compounds. The conductometric titration curves were found to be normal, breaking at 1 : 1 metal-ligand ratio. Molar conductivity data (13–

29 $\Omega^{-1} cm^{-1} mol^{-1}$) in $10^{-3} M$ DMF solution proved the non-ionic nature⁹ of the complexes. On the basis of molecular weights and results of chemical analyses (Table 1), molecular formulas $M(C_4H_8O_3S_5)$, where $M = Mn^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}$, and $\{C_4H_6O_2S_5Cl\}M$, where $M = Fe^{III}$ have been assigned to the xanthato-complexes. Presence of Cl^- ion inside the coordination sphere in Fe^{III} chelate appeared by test only after decomposition of the complex. All the complexes were found thermally stable upto 250° .

Table 1. Analytical and magnetic data of the xanthato complexes

Compd.	Metal%:	μ_{eff} B.M.
	Found (Calcd)	
$C_4H_4OS_5Mn.2H_2O$	17.28 (17.20)	5.89
$C_4H_4OS_5Fe.Cl.H_2O$	16.39 (16.54)	5.95
$C_4H_4OS_5Co.2H_2O$	17.99 (18.22)	3.85
$C_4H_4OS_5Ni.2H_2O$	18.34 (18.17)	2.91
$C_4H_4OS_5Cu.2H_2O$	19.58 (19.37)	1.81

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and S analyses.

Two sharp IR bands at 1112 and $1255 cm^{-1}$ of PTEX were assigned to C–O–C stretching vibrations¹⁰. In the spectra of the xanthates these bands appeared in higher wavelength region at $1120-1130$ and $1257-1270 cm^{-1}$, respectively, suggesting non-involvement of oxygen atom of the C–O–C group. Strong band due to $\nu_{C=S}$ vibrations at $1045 cm^{-1}$ in the spectra of PTEX showed a red-shift in the spectra of the metal xanthates at $1020-1030 cm^{-1}$, indicating involvement of sulfur atom in chelate formation⁵. In the spectra of all the metal chelates, the bands at $3429-3480$, $1629-1640$ and $860-870 cm^{-1}$ were assigned to stretching, deformation and rocking modes of coordinated water¹¹. No change in weight of the complexes was observed on heating upto 250° , which further ruled out possibility of lattice water.

All the complexes were found to be paramagnetic with magnetic moment values corresponding to the spin-only value for unpaired electron (Table 1). These values are in

fair agreement with the reported values observed in high-spin octahedral complexes involving sp^3d^2 hybridization.

In the electronic spectra of the Mn^{II} complex, three bands observed at 14285, 16666 and 19607 cm^{-1} correspond to ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(G)$, ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(G)$ and ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4E_g(G)$ transitions, respectively, suggestive for an octahedral geometry¹². The Fe^{III} complex showed three bands at 14184, 20202 and 24691 cm^{-1} which correspond to transitions ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4A_{1g}(G)$, ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(G)$ and ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4E_g(G)$, respectively, suggesting an octahedral geometry¹³. For the Co^{II} complex, three bands observed at 11976, 17699 and 20408 cm^{-1} which correspond to ${}^4T_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2E_g$, ${}^4T_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}(F)$ and ${}^4T_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$ transitions, respectively, suggesting octahedral geometry^{13,14}. Three bands observed at 10869, 18018 and 25641 cm^{-1} for the Ni^{II} complex correspond to transitions ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}(F)$, ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$ and ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$, respectively, pointing towards an octahedral geometry^{13,15}. The Cu^{II} complex exhibited three absorption bands at 12885, 16940 and 26028 cm^{-1} corresponding to ${}^3B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2A_{2g}(\nu_1)$, ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2B_{2g}(\nu_2)$ and ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2E_{2g}(\nu_3)$ transitions, respectively, indicative of an octahedral geometry¹⁶.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of A.R. grade unless and otherwise specified. Stock solutions of the metal salts (manganese chloride, ferric chloride, cobaltous chloride, nickel chloride and copper acetate) were prepared in double-distilled water and their strengths verified¹⁷. The solutions of desired strengths were made by dilution with water.

Potassium 2-trithiocarbonatoethyl xanthate (PTEX) was prepared by adding 2-mercaptoethanol (1 mol) dropwise in a saturated solution of KOH (2 mol), kept in an ice-bath, followed by addition of carbon disulfide (2 mol) dropwise during 1 h with rapid stirring. The product so obtained was dissolved in acetone (~500 ml). Two layers (upper – yellow and lower – orange red) were separated and the yellow solution was concentrated at 70°, then cooled. The resulting solid was dried with filter strips (yield 60%) and analyzed for sulfur (Found : 52.45. Calcd. 52.29%). The compound was characterized by infrared spectroscopy.

Fresh aqueous solution of PTEX was always used. Both direct and reverse conductometric titrations were performed to decide the composition. The complexes were isolated by mixing equimolecular solutions (0.05 M) of the metal salt and PTEX in 1 : 1 ratio. The resulting compounds were filtered, washed with distilled water, crystallized from etha-

nol, dried in vacuum desiccator over P_2O_5 . The brown coloured complexes were analyzed for metal and sulfur by standard methods¹⁷. The complexes were further characterized by molecular weight (Beckman's cryoscopic method using ethanol solvent), magnetic, electronic and by IR spectral data. Instruments used : Philips conductivity bridge with dip type conductivity cell; Toshniwal CL-49 pH meter; Gouy's magnetic balance model C Meltov Zoric type H16; electronic spectra (ethanol) Shimadzu 1601CP spectrophotometer; IR spectra (KBr) Perkin-Elmer 1600 spectrophotometer; elemental analysis Carlo-Crlea 1106 instrument.

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